

The Playfulness of Interactivity

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Abstract

The last fifteen years have seen a proliferation of interactive media, many of which form a significant part of our everyday experiences. As yet theories of new media have failed to explore the underlying language of interactivity but have focussed rather on an historical relationship to screen theories, socio-linguistic commentary, technological developments and usability theory. This paper re-interprets interactivity as a physical rather than psychological activity and that interaction is a circular process, not simply a mechanism to control devices.

Central to designing for interaction is the phenomenological philosophy of remaining a perpetual beginner, the notion of play and the meditative state that play encourages. Existing works and research are cited that evidence the ability of simple and playful interactions to create successful and emotionally engaging experiences. Two strategies for creating engaging interaction are suggested – playfulness and interaction as content – as is the need to redefine the interface in terms of action and experience rather than objects and information retrieval.

Keywords: Interactivity, play, new media, emotions, design, phenomenology, psychology, games, toys

What is interactivity?

Since the late 80s and early 90s the number of screen-based environments, from art installations to wireless devices, has dramatically increased and many are interactive in some shape or form. They form integral parts of our daily lives and this has been mirrored by a steady increase in the study of usability and information architecture (Garrett 2003; Nielsen 1993; Nielsen and Tahir 2002; Norman 1998; Tufte 1985, 1990, 1997). There is also a body of literature that discusses these 'new media' in terms of their cultural or linguistic forms (Plant 1998; Lovink 2002) and social significance (Haraway 1991; Johnson 1997; Rheingold 1993). These discourses, however, tend to either concentrate on the user's ability to access information or complete tasks as the prime objective of interaction, or concern themselves with the cultural impact of technologies rather than examining the moment and pleasure of interaction in and of itself.

Brenda Laurel's *Computers as Theatre* (1993) is a notable exception in which she explores the parallels between human-computer interaction and dramatic representation and the emotional engagement this entails. More recently, the development of "experience design" (Shedroff 2001) has begun to address the entire user experience, but the processes and

'language' of interactivity – the underlying structures that help to create interactive engagement – are largely under-explored and ill defined.

The question of "What is interactivity?" remains problematic. Lev Manovich's book, *The Language of New Media* (2001) explores new media's heritage of cinema and computer technologies and documents a broad history of work, but his view and definition of new media is only one reading of its genesis. Crucially, Manovich dismisses interactivity as being a fundamental, defining component of new media instead arguing that all texts and art are interactive for they require the "psychological process of filling-in, hypothesis formation, recall, and identification, which are required for us to comprehend [them]" (Manovich 2001: 57). Manovich avoids using the term 'interactive' because he suggests, "there is a danger that we will interpret 'interaction' literally." That is, that interaction will relate to the physical aspects of interaction (with buttons, mouse and the screen) "at the expense of psychological interaction" (Ibid.).

Yet it is precisely Manovich's literal definition of new media, of the physical coming together of cinema and computers with Konrad Zuse's use of old film as a punch-card programming system, that prevents him from being able to include interactivity within his theoretical framework. Part of the difficulty arises from Manovich drawing so heavily upon cinematic theory, which concerns itself primarily with the psychological relationship between viewer and moving image. The nature of story structure and plot, character and action have been explored since the days of Aristotle's *Poetics* (Roberts and Bywater 1954) in order to understand how to engage the audience in the emotional and spiritual journeys of the characters. Cinema's notion of mise-en-scene utilises the relationship of the camera to the subject, the lighting, the angles, the editing, and the costumes to enhance the emotional subtext of the story and draw audiences in to the world of the film. In this framework there is no space for physical (as opposed to psychological) interactivity. As author of *The Playful World* (2000) Mark Pesce suggests, "Cinema is the true lean-back medium because you suspend everything else – it is storytelling and you don't talk over the storyteller " (Polaine, 2004). By using cinema as a starting point we come no closer to defining interactivity.

From navigational menus to videogames, interactivity is often part of an interface to other content. This ignores the experience of the moment of interaction and relegates it to a

mechanism of control at best and something to be mastered and 'got through' at worst. Brenda Laurel (1993) argues that we have this relationship the wrong way around.

Action is indeed the primary component of human-computer activity – not environments, interfaces, or objects. But environments, interfaces, and objects are traditionally much easier to conceive of and represent than a quality that is fundamentally invisible, and the structure of which is contested at best (Laurel 1993: 135).

In design, this inevitably leads to the focus on the technology and interface rather than the emotional experience of the interaction. Laurel continues:

What if we were to define the action of information retrieval, not as looking for something, but examining or experiencing it? This seemingly innocuous shift in point of view puts the emphasis in an entirely different domain: the action involved in perceiving, interpreting, and experiencing information (Laurel 1993: 140).

Taking this view, the focus of design shifts from designing interfaces to designing interactions and interactive experiences. Laurel compares engagement in interactive experiences to the theatrical notion of “willing suspension of disbelief” introduced by the early nineteenth-century poet Samuel Taylor Coleridge (Laurel 1993: 113). Willing suspension of disbelief in traditional narrative is the audience’s willingness to “play along” and pretend that the fictional world presented to them really exists in order to become engrossed in the story.

In a computer's operating system of course we all know that the windows, folders and files are not 'really' there, they do not really exist as the physical objects the icons represent, but in order to engage with either the task in hand or the pleasure of the experience (in a game, for example) we willingly pretend that they are. How can we utilise this disbelief to create an engaging and absorbing interaction in the same way that plot, character and mise-en-scene engage the audience in the emotional arcs of story and disengage them from the reality of their world? What, for example, is the equivalent of a camera angle or mood lighting in interaction?

To try and answer these questions this paper suggests a different definition of interactivity to that of Manovich, one in which the physical interaction is a key component. In this physical

definition of interactivity an 'interactor' makes a change to the device presented to them (usually to elements on a screen, but not exclusively) which in turn changes his or her own behaviour. In a complete interaction the participant's changed behaviour creates another change in the device's reaction, which results in another change in the interactor's behaviour, thus producing a feedback loop of interaction. This idea of a physical-virtual feedback loop allows us to escape Manovich's psychological definition of interaction and looks beyond the concerns of interface and usability by referring back to action as Laurel (1993) suggests. This form of action, reaction and interaction is also a fundamental part of play and game playing (Caillois 2001; Huizinga 1955) which forms one of the principles of designing for interaction outlined below.

"Discovering" interactivity

In 1994 the new media collective Antirom produced an eponymous CD-ROM that was intended as a "critique of the poverty of contemporary multimedia" (Allenson et al. 1994). Antirom's interests, research and projects were fuelled by a desire to try and "discover" the interactive equivalents to cinematic language, very much in the modernist tradition of attempting to discover the 'essence' of a medium (Cameron 1998).

The Antirom members felt that many of the early 90s commercial interactive multimedia outpourings (mainly kiosks and CD-ROMS) consisted of "ill-conceived point-and-click 3D interfaces" (Allenson et al., 1994) grafted onto re-purposed old media content such as video, text, images and audio. The *Xplora* CD-ROM by musician and artist Peter Gabriel (1993) is one such example. Although *Xplora* was a polished and popular production, the interactivity within it mainly consisted of navigational elements that aided (or in the case of the VIP area, hindered) access to video and audio samples of Gabriel's musical works. As such, the interactivity was little more than database access and VCR button functionality.

Figure 1, a screenshot from the 1994 Antirom CD-ROM. Users click and re-mix audio and rotating body sections in an interactive rendition of the traditional 'Misfits' children's book.

Antirom sought to address this by creating interactive works in which the interface *was* the content and the purpose of the interaction was the *experience of the interaction*, not a vehicle to access another, old-media, experience. The original Antirom CD-ROM (and subsequent projects such as an installation for the Barbican's JAM exhibition [Allenson et al.,1996] and several installations, kiosks and CD-ROMs for Levis Strauss and Co. Ltd.) consisted of a collection of simple interactive experiments.

These interactives became known as toys because of the nature of the audience's interaction with them – most of these toys were playful and created an engaging diversion, without having the kinds of goals or competitiveness of games – the pleasure of was in the playing. Each interactive deliberately utilised only one or two simple forms of interaction, such as moving the mouse around the screen or rolling over different elements, so that the interactor might become absorbed by the experience of interaction rather than being frustrated by the interface.

Figure 2, the "Production" section of the Levi's kiosk design by Antirom (Allenson, et al. 1996). This section replaced a tedious video documentary and allowed users to interact directly with a simplified version of the manufacturing process with each process being turned into an interactive "toy".

One example is the "soundspace" audio mixer. Rather than re-creating a virtual version of a real audio mixer complete with 3D rendered buttons and sliders, the Antirom designers simply assigned sounds to matching graphical elements on the screen. In one version this was a scan of a toy horse, a dollar sign and a sheriff's badge. Each represents a sound (horses galloping, Western music, and cowboy dialogue) and each can be dragged around the screen. The volume of each sound is determined by the proximity of the mouse to the object and the user interacts directly with the content to create the audio mix of their choice.

Figure 3, a simple 'soundspace' audio mixer from the Antirom CD-ROM.

Difficulties arise when trying to explain exactly *why* one toy or 'interactive' is more engaging than another. Engagement in this sense uses Laurel's comparison to "willing suspension of disbelief" in theatre – how engrossed in the experience and action of the interactivity the interactor becomes. However, as Lev Manovich admits, "Although it is relatively easy to specify different interactive structures used in new media objects, it is much more difficult to deal theoretically with users' experiences of these structures. This aspect of interactivity remains one of the most difficult theoretical questions raised by new media" (Manovich 2001: 56).

Playful interaction and direct manipulation

The work and research conducted at Antirom (and by its members subsequently in other institutions) has found two main factors that contribute to an engaging interaction; these are playfulness and making the experience of an interaction the "content" or primary aim. Although graphics, sounds, spectacle and occasionally narrative may all play their part in the overall experience of an interactive work, the Antirom designers found that they were often secondary to the interactivity. Interactive "engines" (code with placeholder graphics) were usually designed first and appropriate content inserted after several prototypes were made. This process is much closer to those of product design and engineering than graphic design

(which has since become the dominant design discipline of the Web). This is not to say that the audio-visual treatment of an interactive is inconsequential, it is an essential factor to an engaging piece, but rather that the interactivity was a more important starting point. A beautiful but tedious interaction remains a tedious interaction regardless of the graphical treatment.

Starting from a basic interactive principle (rolling the mouse around the screen, for example) and stripping back extraneous elements allowed the Antirom designers to explore interactivity in its own right. This means there is almost no interface learning process for the 'interactor', but another kind of learning does take place, one that was found to be an important factor in engagement and akin to notions of play.

By dissolving the interface and allowing people to interact directly with the content on the screen, the interactor can engage not in the process of learning *how* to use the interface, but rather *what they can achieve* within the "rules of interaction" set up by the author of the work. This principle is clearly demonstrated in a simple interactive from the Benetton Research and Development Communication Centre, Fabbrica, in Italy.

Rimbalzo (Fabbrica 2001) is an interactive sound toy that uses an image of a moulded concrete wall as its 'interface' and also the graphic content. When one clicks on one of the moulding indents, it falls from the wall like a ball and bounces on the ground producing a simple kalimba (thumb piano) note. The "ball" bounces back to its original position and falls again bouncing and producing the sound ad infinitum. The time interval between bounces and the pitch of the note is defined by the height of the ball on the wall. When several balls are bouncing at once they produce a phased rhythm and musical sequence entirely dependent on the moment in time each ball is set in motion.

The interaction itself is incredibly simple; one can click on the balls or click on the reset button. The pleasure and engagement comes not from learning how this interaction works but in trying to 'play' the interactive as an instrument, to try and become better at creating more ordered or desirable phasing patterns rather than a random cacophony (which is also possible).

Figure 4, *Rimbalzo* by Fabrice in Italy.
Each moulding recess becomes a bouncing 'ball' when clicked.

There is a body of material from sociology and psychology (Caillois 2001; Huizinga 1955) concerning the experience of play, which is pertinent to understanding the pleasure of play in interaction here, much of which concerns the role of rules in games and which is outside of the scope of this paper. Winnicott's (2001) view of play is that it operates in a halfway world between our inner and outer worlds. More importantly, he defines play as both a meditative space and highlights the physical movements associated with play in his summary of children at play:

"The area of playing is not inner psychic reality. It is outside the individual, but it is not the external world [...] Playing involves the body because of the manipulation of objects [...] Playing is essentially satisfying." (Winnicott 2001: 51-52)

Mark Pesce believes that Sony's camera-based games using the Eye Toy on the PlayStation 2 represents a fundamental shift in interactivity. "If you show it to a three year-old, who doesn't have fine motor skills, they immediately understand how to play. It has removed the idea of the interface, it has made the interface completely invisible as far as they are concerned [...] their body has become the affordance" (Pesce 2004). Pesce argues that this kind of playful interaction connects with us at a deep level in the same manner as Aristotle's dramatic arcs and believes these are probably hard-wired into our psyches (Polaine, 2004).

Designing for interaction

One of the features of play is that it is held to be 'not serious' and is easily dismissed, but because it is 'not serious' it matters less when one makes mistakes. Most designers will be aware of the power of prototyping, role-playing and brainstorming, all of which require a suspension of judgement and the willingness to 'play along' in order to discover something new and break free of traditional thinking.

Indeed as children we learn about the world through play, we come to understand how language, human relationships, physics and our own bodies work to name but a few of the enormous learning tasks that face an infant and all of which involve making mistakes by necessity. Yet as we mature play becomes an activity dismissed as childish and not serious and the need to stop making mistakes is drummed into us via our educational systems (which privilege results over process).

Cameron's (1998) modernist approach of uncovering the "essence" of interactivity can be viewed within the philosophical framework of phenomenology as described by Merleau-Ponty (2002). This phenomenological approach advocates, not a total disconnection with experience in order to understand it in a reductive, Cartesian sense, but rather a "distancing" that allows us to step back from our entanglement and re-create our naivety, to remain the "perpetual beginner" as Eric Matthews (2002) describes it. In this view human beings "are part of the world that they experience, and who experience it, not in the form of pure contemplation, but in the course of active involvement with it" (Matthews 2002: 35).

It is via this approach that it is possible to both explore the structures of engagement (as one might discuss the story and character in a traditional narrative) but remain open to the

possibilities and experiences of new and interesting modes of interactivity. There appears to be a direct parallel here between Merleau-Ponty's (2002) attempts to escape the dry, logical Cartesian view of being via phenomenological philosophy and the traditional battle lines often drawn between programmers or engineers (who literally work within Cartesian space) and designers' desires to utilise the emotive properties of objects, graphics, spaces and interactions.

Significantly, the process of 'discovering' these interactions at Antirom was through an iterative design process that required the willingness to make many mistakes, as Andy Cameron wrote in 1998, "We have not discarded lines of enquiry merely because they appeared to be ridiculous or stupid, and we have made as many mistakes as we could, as quickly as we could" (Cameron 1998). It would seem appropriate, therefore, that this kind of playful approach to design can also help us understand how to design for playful interaction in a media form which is still in its infancy.

Towards a language of interactivity

Without a clear understanding of the language and nature of interactivity, interactive media will continue to be a fractured and emotionally barren landscape. Although literature concerning video game culture is a useful addition (for example Herz 1997), video games set up a number of conditions, such as competitive strategies and visceral experiences, that bring interaction into a rather different, hyperactive zone. Competition and goal-based gameplay tends to overshadow the interaction itself and interface is again reduced to a functional role. The notion of play applied to the realm of interactivity provides a way forward beyond the limits of media forms and usability and a possible solution to the theoretical difficulties with interactivity that Manovich discusses.

Merleau-Ponty's ethos of remaining a perpetual beginner and Winnicott's notion of play and the almost naïve meditative state that play induces can be useful design guides. By narrowing our focus to the moment of interaction and developing interactive "toys" in which the interface is dissolved and the interactivity is paramount we are a little closer to grasping the principles of engaging interactions. It is hoped that these explorations can help the field of interactivity move beyond a blinkered focus on technology and develop a coherent theory of

interactivity that mirrors the theories of cinema without being simple transpositions of one media's theoretical framework onto another cultural form.

In turn, these principles may then be applied to a wider range of objects and interfaces in which interaction plays a role. As the developed Western world escalates our options for leisure pursuits whilst simultaneously increasing the amount of stress that making these choices involves, developing playful diversions and understanding of how playfulness can be woven into everyday interactions may prove to be an ever more important consideration for designers and the basis for future research.

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